

Cos4Cloud

**Co-designed Citizen Observatories Services for the
EOS-Cloud**

H2020 programme: Research and Innovation action

**Deliverable 4.1
General Purpose integration platform**

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R	Document, report excluding the periodic and final reports	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	X
DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, photos, etc.	
SOF	Software, technical diagram, etc.	
OTHER	Flyers, etc.	

Dissemination level		
PU	Public, fully open.	X
CO	Confidential, restricted under conditions set out in Model Grant Agreement	
CI	Classified	

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Executive Summary

The Interactive Platforms for data integration will allow users to interact simultaneously with different sources of data to create derived services. The base of the development will be a generic purpose platform that can be customized according to specific needs. The expert platform will be able to exchange information with different modules using the standard protocols defined in WP2. This generic platform will incorporate microservices that will allow the external users, use or integrate each service in their own institutional or professional web platform.

To develop this platform, the first task that we had to tackle was to create a common framework that helps us and helps others to build their own Biodiversity Observation Expert Portal. This portal provides very interesting functionalities for the community, and solves several problems that have arisen in recent years due to the increase in the number of Citizen Observatories (COs) that have been created without following common rules. Some of these problems are:

- Each Citizen Observatory (CO) uses their own species list.
- Each CO uses their own structure of meta-information.
- The researchers have to spend a lot of time searching observations in different places.
- There is no interaction between experts from the different COs.
- Experts must spend a lot of time, if they want to contribute with their identifications in several COs. This means that the number of identifications in some cases are poor and also it takes too long time until an observation is identified or validated, therefore, many users from COs are unhappy because their observations are not validated, causing a loss of users.
- There is a limited or in some cases inexistent recognition for the contributions of the citizens

The identification of these problems allows us to think about some **solutions** that the Experts' Portal could cover and at the same time let us to discover the strengths that this software could have:

- The Expert portal should use a **common species list (GBIF Backbone)** for all the Observations from the different COs integrated in the current phase.
- The Expert portal should use **a standardized information (Darwin core)** that allows representing all the meta-information from the different COs with the same format.

- The Expert portal should include a **global search** that allows the experts to search and filter observations from the different COs.
- The standardization and common species list solutions will allow the experts to reduce the time that they invest when they want to **download all the information** from different COs with the **same structure**.
- The Expert portal should send all the identifications and comments that their experts add to the original COs, in this line, there will be more experts that could contribute with their identifications to different COs, that **increase the interaction between platforms** and experts.

But in addition to all of these problems and solutions, we had to keep in mind the User Experience that the citizens and experts already have in the existing COs. For this reason, one of other important task that we did, it was to analyze the common functionalities that the COs, involved on the Cos4Cloud project, have:

- Login.
- Internationalization.
- Search by species.
- Search by place.
- Filters.
- List of results.
- Observation detail.
- Show minimum information of each observation such as: image, proposed name, scientific name, location, observation date, source platform, id,...
- Option to include comments and identifications

Our goal, with this list of minimum, but very necessary functionalities, has been to create a powerful service, but with an easy and usable interface that allows to the experts to:

- Find species in different Observatories searching in one place.
- Contribute with more identifications in less time.
- Download information from different COs in one place.
- Download standardized information with a common structure.
- Increase the interactions between the experts from the different COs.
- Engage more experts using biodiversity standards well-known by them and used in the Global Community.
- Increase the collaborative work.
- Log in to the system using a federated login system.
- Use as a research tool.

But this service is not just thought for the experts, it will be a very useful tool for other kinds of users who will be able to:

- Find validated information by professionals.
- Use it as an educational tool.

- Get images of some specific species.
- Get inspired by other Citizen Science projects.
- Create a community of observers and experts.

Besides all of these advantages, the Expert Portal may include more Biodiversity and Environmental COs in the future, in an easy way, without complex integration process, complying with the FAIR data rules that will allow integrating this service in the EOSC Hub to get more visibility, support and engagement

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1.Methodological approaches

Before beginning to describe the procedure that we have carried out, we are going to present the methodology that we have followed, designed by Science for Change. This methodology is based on two fundamental pillars for each Cos4Cloud service:

- Co-design.
- Agile methodology.

Co-design is an approach to creative practice that enables a wide range of people to make a creative contribution in the formulation and solution of a problem. It's often used as an umbrella term for:

- Co-creation.
- Open design process.
- Participatory design process.
- Design thinking process.

And reflects a fundamental change in the traditional designer-client relationship. (<http://designforeurope.eu/what-Co-design>)

Figure 1.1. Co-design. Science for Change.

In this process the users are considered “experts” of their own experience and their needs and concerns become central to the design process. Their role is to provide ways to communicate, be creative, share insights and test out new ideas.

There are three terms that help describe a Co-design process:

DESIGN THINKING: an approach to designing that supports innovation and intelligent change. It is a human-centered approach which is driven by creative and analytical thinking, customer empathy and iterative learning.

DESIGN PROCESS: a systematic problem-solving strategy, with criteria and constraints, used to develop many possible solutions to solve or satisfy human needs or wants and to narrow down the possible solutions to one final choice.

DESIGN METHODS: procedures and techniques for designing. There are hundreds of methods that a designer might use within a design process. Since co-creation was created, design methods are the tools that designers use to externalize the design process, to let anyone be a designer

So **design thinking** would be the big umbrella under which a design or a Co-design process can be defined, using design methods and techniques. The design thinking approach is described by a challenge or need as starting point, a final implementation of the solution, and 5 stages in between:

- EMPATHIZE (know the context and the users).
- DEFINE (frame the needs/ challenges/ objectives).
- IDEATE (think of possible solutions).
- PROTOTYPE (select an idea, prototype, validate, repeat).
- TEST (evaluate the prototype).

The first two stages will help understanding the situation, the third one will help explore possible solutions, and the last two will help materialize the selected solution.

In the case of the development of the General Purpose Platform, we use Co-design as a service based on several pillars:

- **Documentation.** A place where the partners of the project can share and store all the documents being developed and the different versions of the services being developed.
- **Interaction.** A place where the partners can easily give and receive feedback, as well as establish dialogues on the design of the services.
- **Co-creation.** A place where the Co-design community can perform an online workshop for each service, so that we can gather their opinions on usability, desirability, and general improvement of the service.

The digital tools that we used to perform the Co-design phases during the first period were:

Figure 1.2. Co-design digital tools. Science for Change.

In order to carry out this Co-design process both internally and externally, we have followed the phases defined by Science for Change in the next diagram:

Figure 1.3. Co-design process. Science for Change.

In addition to applying the Co-design / Co-Creation methodology during the development, we cannot forget the need to apply an agile methodology. To do this, we rely on the procedures agreed in the deliverable 2.2 **Agile Methodology**, in which several cycles were established during the process:

- Regular MvE planning.
- Iterative development.
- Co-design workshops.
- Science and technology coordination.

Within an agile process the team was working on a backlog to discuss, prioritize, and reference actual workload. We take part on the bi-weekly SciTech meetings and actively seek feedback from the group regarding UI, concrete CO integration, or particular features like back-channeling comments to the actual CO.

To coordinate service integration, we use the service documentation site on the Confluence to document metadata of the service and integration aspects with other

services. We also do continuous deployment to demonstrate working software and provide an integration endpoint of the latest version:

<https://github.com/Bineo-Consulting/Cos4Cloud>

The process binds to regular Co-design workshops. The raw results will be digested to user stories and placed in the backlog, in the case of the Expert Portal we use Monday tool to create our particular backlog:

Subelementos	EP	Labels	Status	P. Coordinat...	P.Manager	Assigned To	Progress	Schedule
Deliverable D4.1	EP110	Documentation	Done		MP	RG	100%	ene. 1 - nov.
Migration Cos4Cloud IT	EP109	Infrastructure	External dependence		RG	RG	0%	nov. 14 -
Diagram explanation Expert Portal	EP108	Documentation	Done		MP	MP	100%	sep. 22 -
MS15 - Prototype of INTS service for Biodiv. monitoring re...	EP107	Documentation	Done		MP	MP	100%	may. 1 - sep.
Arreglar Front	EP106	CO implementation	Done		MP	RG	100%	sep. 1 - 3
Conexión API STA	EP105	Interoperability	Stuck		MP	RG	0%	sep. 1 - oct.
Naturfera	EP104	CO imple... Interop.	Done		MP	RG	100%	sep. 1 - 3
Back implementation	EP103	Environment Back	Done		MP	RG	100%	sep. 1 - nov.

Subelementos	EP	Menú desplegable	P.Coordinat...	P. Manager	AssignedTo	Progreso	Schedule	Status	Deadline
SP9: Setup isomorphic render pages (R...	EP103	Environment		MP	RG	0%	oct. 19 - 31	Stuck	nov. 1, 2020
Changes SP8	EP102	Development		MP	RG	100%	-	Done	
Review SP8	EP101	Co-Design		MP	MP	100%	-	Done	
Testing	EP100	Testing		MP	MP	0%	-	External dependence	
SP8: Setup Docker	EP99	Environment		MP	RG	100%	oct. 1 - 17	Done	nov. 1, 2020
Changes SP7	EP98	Development		MP	RG	100%	-	Done	
Review SP7	EP97	Co-Design		MP	MP	100%	-	Done	
Testing	EP96	Testing		MP	MP	0%	-	External dependence	
SP7: Download Observations Controller	EP95	Interopers... Notific...		MP	RG	0%	oct. 1 - 10	Stuck	nov. 1, 2020
Changes SP6	EP94	Development		MP	RG	100%	-	Done	
Review SP6	EP93	Co-Design		MP	MP	100%	-	Done	
Testing	EP92	Testing		MP	MP	100%	-	Done	
SP6: Species Controller	EP91	Interopers... Environ...		MP	RG	100%	sep. 21 - 30	Done	nov. 1, 2020
Changes SP5	EP90	Development		MP	RG	100%	-	Done	
Review SP5	EP89	Co-Design		MP	MP	100%	-	Done	

Figure 1.4. Backlog Monday.

Once referenced from the service documentation page the input can serve as discussion input for the twelve weekly MvE increment planning as well.

In the next diagram we can see the tools that we use during all of this process to interact with the internal/external experts, and document all the information.

Figure 1.5. Co-design and Agile tools.

2. Analysis

2.1 Introduction

During the process of Co-design used in this point, the end user (scientists, experts and citizens who make observations) participate in the definition of their needs, through direct interaction with the development team in which:

- New ideas are generated and effective and better focused solutions are offered.
- The knowledge of the more technical profiles and the profiles that will be potential users of the service once finished is collected.
- The integration of the opinions and perspectives of the different profiles involved are facilitated.

We use the Design Thinking methodology that allows us to: achieve effective, innovative and useful solutions that meet the needs of users and define the requirements that we present in section [1.Methodological approaches](#).

"Design Thinking: Empathize, define, devise, prototype and test".

As we already defined in the Executive summary section, Design Thinking is a methodology to generate innovative ideas based on knowledge and understanding. It allows to offer solutions that can be executed at a technical level, based on the needs of the users, seeking to add value and ease in decision-making when it comes to knowing in which points a greater effort must be made, thanks to the knowledge of the end-user problems and needs. This methodology is divide in the next stages:

- [Empathize](#).
- [Define](#).

- [Ideate](#).
- [Prototype](#)
- [Test](#)

All the outputs generated during these stages have been documented on Confluence and presented during the Technical meetings, and to the rest of partners via Steering Committee Meetings, General Meetings.

2.2 Co-design inputs

As a result of the Co-Creation process, explained during the Methodology section, and applied at the following Co-design activities we consolidated a list of initial requirements that were considered during the development. The first Co-design meetings were held internally in the technical meetings (conformed by the TICs component of the Cos4Cloud consortium) every 15 days to present, discuss and co-create the Expert Portal with the people participating in each of them. The General Meeting and Annual Meeting of the Consortium, were also used to carry out Co-Creation exercises with the rest of the partners. The feedback obtained allowed us to define little by little the most relevant functionalities that the Portal should have.

Besides that, it was important to have the opinion of people outside the project, so we planned, with the Co-design team led by the partner Science for Change, workshops with groups of external experts who contribute their ideas about the work developed. These workshops will allow us to improve and make experts part of the whole Co-Creation process. Up until today, we have already carried out one of the Co-design workshops with more than 30 people who have provided us very useful information about the Expert Portal. All of their feedback will help us develop in an agile way a better solution adapted to their needs.

Co-design activities implemented for Cos4Bio

- Sci&Tech meetings: bimonthly since April 2020
- General meeting (June 2020): integration of services with Cos4Cloud citizen observatories
- Initial meeting with experts (August 2020): experts from citizen observatories
- Annual meeting (November 2020): key performance index for services
- Co-design workshop (March 2021): stakeholders and end users

We could extract in a collaborative way, with the help of the experts a list of minimum functionalities to take into account when developing the Portal of Experts. These list of inputs are:

- Federated login system using the Authenix service.
- Data integration with various citizen science platforms.

- Recommended to use if it's possible free and open software.
- Interoperability layer.
- Search with filters.
- Spatial search.
- FAIR data compliant.
- Download data in CSV format.
- Integration with a common species list.

In addition to this list of inputs, we also extract with the help of the experts a list of different kind of requirements according to the FURPS + model [Grady 92]:

- Functional requirements:
 - The system must have a federated authentication system making use of the Authenix service.
 - Simple searches by name must be possible.
 - It should be possible to perform simple searches with filters.
 - It must be possible to perform spatial searches.
 - A list of the results obtained from the search carried out must be displayed with minimal information: image, name, data source platform, number of identifications, number of comments.
 - The detailed view of the observation must be accessible.
 - It must be possible to include a comment, as long as the user is logged in.
 - It must be possible to include an identification, as long as the user is logged in.
- Usability
 - Home page.
 - Brief information on the cards for each observation.
 - Accessible login button.
 - Simple search engine without many interactions.
 - Well structured information in the detail of the file of each observation.
 - Warning messages in case of error.
- Reliability:
 - The system, being in connection with other portals, must foresee the failure of external services, with the main objective of knowing how to handle their non-response, and thus be able to guarantee the correct operation of the service despite them.

- Performance:
 - Response time: Response time will depend on the response times of each external COs, so maybe we should define a maximum wait time in which a CO has to reponse.
 - Availability: The service will always be available

- Support:
 - The system will present support for internationalization in several languages, although initially only an interface will be presented in English.
 - Ease of maintenance: It is developed to be easy to maintain, thinking about the future of the project.
 - Adaptability: based on a component model, it can be easily adapted to the environment in which you want to work and can be tested locally.

- Implementation:
 - Free tools should be used.
 - Standards should be used in the development.
 - Interaction with an interoperability layer.

- Legal:
 - Licenses: Everyone who uses the system must use a CC BY SA NC license.
 - The development is done with privacy by design and conforms to the GDPR regulations (personal information is very broad and can even consist of only GPS coordinates)
 - Photos with licenses for use will also not be hosted on the system, they will simply be displayed using the source URL.

It's important to say that to follow all of these process we have used the tools commented in the Methodology section

- Documentation tool: Confluence.
- Interaction tool: Go-Meeting.
- Agile platform: Monday.

2.3 Stages

2.3.1 Empathize

In a first stage, we must empathize with the problems or needs that users and platforms have. So, with the help of the Co-design team, we must represent the

knowledge contributed by the different members of the group that interacts with the platform, with the main objective of speeding up and facilitating the identification and classification of scientific information related to biodiversity that meets on all four platforms.

The conclusion we can draw from all of them is that the platform will be a tremendously useful and productive tool for users who require it, reducing their investigation times, giving visibility to the observations published by citizens and increasing the commitment of experts.

To facilitate this work, we have carried out an analysis of the 4th Biodiversity platforms involved in the project. This analysis of the portals allows us to see the strengths and common lines that we must try to follow.

2.3.1.1 iSpotNature

Web: <https://www.ispotnature.org/>

Language: English only, although there is a language selector.

Login: Accessible, well located. The registration form is too long and login should take precedence.

Home: The menu starts as the most important element with an initially confusing explore button since it appears to be a search engine and yet it is a navigation through the website. Very soon all the observations are shown as well as those that need to be identified, this is very positive for the user. It also includes filters through icons that help to quickly visualize the species we want to find (it should be added that these filters work a bit slow). We also can find on this view articles and news that allows the user to keep up to date with news.

On the right we can see a sidebar that includes additional information.

- Location with a map.
- Search in iSpot.
- Login.
- Information of new news (projects and social networks).

Observation detail: The detail of each observation consists of its photographs and its detailed information, in addition, it suggests other observations and finally shows the comments related to the observation.

Additional: We find more sections that we do not analyze in depth because they are not in connection with the project.

Adapted to mobile: Yes.

2.3.1.2 Artportalen

Web: <https://www.artportalen.se/>

It has a tutorial that explains how to use the platform. Very positive for the new user.

Language: In Swedish, and it has a selector that is not very accessible since it is only shown if the flag is clicked, to switch to English.

Login: Well located in the upper right (as in the previous platform). The button does not stand out from the rest. The registration form is well dimensioned, it is not heavy to fill out.

Home: Featured articles and news related to the platform and its contents are presented.

Search: Really tedious to use, endless fields to fill out. This makes it a very accurate search engine, but not very attractive. It is a portal highly focused on specialists looking for specific data on Biodiversity.

View list: List with all observers classified by total number of observations

Media: Grid of observations without filters.

Observation detail: We can see the photograph and below the information.

Additional: Inside we find more sections that we will not analyze in depth because they are not related to our project.

Adapted to mobile: No

2.3.1.3 Natusfera

Web: <https://natusfera.gbif.es/>

Language: Accessible from the main page in Spanish, Catalan, English, Basque, Galician and Italian. Once you browse it is difficult to find a way to change the language, only through the account settings or turning back to the home page.

Login: Well located at the top right. The registration form is well dimensioned and it is not heavy to fill out.

Home: It shows data on the platform of the number of observations, species and people that are part of it, accompanied by images and a map (very visual) within a slider. The next section is a well-summarized guide on how the platform works. The contents are well classified in the top menu and therefore easy to read.

Observation detail: We can see on a map the observations made in a certain location, accompanied by a sidebar in which we find a list of pictures and a brief information per each.

Species: We find a view well classified by types of species where we can explore each of the types in detail.

Additional: We find more sections inside that we will not analyze in depth because they are not in connection with the project.

Adapted to mobile: Yes

2.3.1.4 PlantNet

Web: <https://plantnet.org/en/>

Home: It focuses on making a donation to the project and downloading its application. The reasons for participating are explained below, followed by the content of the platform. Later, a section with other applications created by the PI@ntNet family and finally content of a social and contact nature.

Observation detail: It contains the information and then the photographs taken by the user.

Desktop version: We found a set of cards containing information based on different parameters that can be explored. Within each tab we see a list with the photos uploaded by users alphabetically ordered preceded by a search engine. These can be viewed in detail with additional information.

Adapted to mobile: Yes

2.3.2 Define

Once we finished the analysis stage, we defined with the experts who could be the potential users of the platform. Mainly they will be experts capable of identifying species, but also citizens interested in knowing more about biodiversity, environmental variables and involved in citizen science.

These are the profiles that will be involved in the portal:

Table of users	
Role	What will they find on the platform?
New user	Easy registration intuitive interface Familiar interface <study of other platforms> Simple learning process Ease to understand how the platform works
Expert user	Well classified information Easy access to information Easy to see news
New expert	Intuitive actions Similarity to known platforms Simple learning process
Senior expert	Easy export of information Quick access to information Well classified and filtered information

On the other hand, we defined the type user of our platform, which could be a person with the following characteristics:

- Approximate age between 25 and 65 years.
- Interested in citizen science, biodiversity, environmental variables and sustainability.
- and with advanced knowledge about identification and validation of biodiversity observations and environmental measurements.

2.3.3 Ideate

In this stage we begin to shape the user flows and sitemap of the platform represented with several diagrams that help us to better understand the objectives, functionalities

and flows defined during the different technical meetings, before to go to the next stage.

- [Flow Diagram](#)
- [Task Flow Diagram](#)
- [UI Flow Diagram](#)
- [Site Map Diagram](#)
- [Wireframes](#)

All these diagrams also helped us to realize when we defined something wrong in terms of information flow, some useless functionalities, or when we forgot to take something into account.

2.3.3.1 Flow Diagram

The objective of the flowchart is to represent the actions that users will be able to take to complete the different processes covered by the general-purpose platform.

Figure 2.1. Flow Diagram

During the review of the requirements and the first version of the diagram in one of the technical meetings, we realized that we had to change several of the functionalities that we define at the beginning:

- There are no profiles.
- The Experts portal never validates data, because each Citizen Observatory has their own rules to validate the information.
- We have to follow the GDPR rules
- And we have to integrate an external federate authentication system (Authenix).

2.3.3.2 Task Flow Diagram

Task flows focus on how users travel through the platform while performing a specific task. They generally show only one path and don't include multiple branches or pathways like a traditional user flow might. These are best used when the task being analyzed is accomplished similarly by all users. When using task flows, it is assumed that all users will share a common starting point and have no variability in the way the task is carried out.

Figure 2.2. Login. Task Flow

Figure 2.3. Search by name. Task Flow

Figure 2.4. Search by Filters. Task Flow

Figure 2.5. Search by Area. Task Flow

Figure 2.6. Add identification. Task Flow

Figure 2.7. Add comment. Task Flow

Figure 2.8. Add identification and comment. Task Flow

2.3.3.3 UI Flow Diagram

User interface flow diagrams are typically used for two purposes. First, they are used to model the interactions that users have with the software, as defined in a single use case. For example, can refer to several screens and provide insight into how they are used. Based on this information, we are going to develop a user interface-flow diagram that reflects the behavioral view of the single use case. Second, they enable us to gain a high-level overview of the user interface for the Expert Portal.

This overview is effectively the combination of all the behavioral views derived from our use cases, the result being called the architectural view of the interface.

Figure 2.9. UI Flow

2.3.3.4 Site Map Diagram

A sitemap is a list or diagram that helps you plan out your website. It should contain all the pages of a website in a way that shows how the user will access them, starting with the homepage and branching out to include all the subpages.

Figure 2.10. Site Map 1

Figure 2.11. Site Map 2

2.3.3.5 Wireframes

Wireframes are a combination of wireflows and flowcharts. They are a simplified visual guide that represents the framework of a website. Wireframes on their own help convey the design on each individual page, but lack the ability to communicate the page-to-page flow of heavily dynamic interfaces. Besides the Wireframes allows us to add a page context to UX flows and analyze how their experience impacts the user experience through the app or website.

On the other hand the wireframes also let us define a roadmap to follow for predetermined functionality and content that aims to achieve a specific goal.

Following we can see the different wireframes that compose the Expert Portal.

Figure 2.12: In this wireframe, we can see in the header of the Home, the Cos4Cloud logo, the language selector, the log in and the notifications button. Next the cover text and the search by species or by place, followed by the filters and search buttons. Finally, a list of the observations ordered by date is displayed.

Figure 2.12. Wireframe Home view with header and search section

Figure 2.13: We can see on the top right the options to change the language, login and the notifications.

Figure 2.13. Choose language options and notifications.

Figure 2.14: In figure 2.14 we see the footer with the following sections: About, Help, Privacy Policy, Terms of Service, Contact and the links to social networks.

Figure 2.14. Footer

Figure 2.15: In this figure we can see how it is possible to search by species, and by place where the observation was made, and also we can see that the result of the search or the filter applied can be exported to a CSV file.

Figure 2.15. Search by species and places. Export the information to a csv file.

Figure 2.16: In this figure, we can see the different types of filters that can be applied: type of observation (plantae, animalia, fungi, reptilia) information source portal (Natusfera, iSpot, ArtPortalen and PlantNet), observation quality (research, casual, with geo, with photos). In the future we want to include more filters.

Figure 2.16. Filter information. Export the information to a csv file.

Figure 2.17: In this wireframe we can see the Observation detail with the next information: Photography, scientific name, characteristics of the observation, when the observation was made, information source portal, latitude and longitude where it was taken, comments made by other users, species search, as well as the possibility of adding new comments and identifications.

Hohenbuehelia petaloïdes (casual)

🕒 1h 🗨️ 0 ✎️ 1 🖼️ 3

🌐 Natusfera

📍 Lat 399750352999, Lon -0.3050320777

Comments

 CANDIDO SOS has identified this observation 1h

 Hohenbuehelia petaloïdes

Add comment/identification

🔍 Search species

Comments

Enter any notes here...

ADD IDENTIFICATION

Figure 2.17. Observation detail.

2.3.4 Prototype

As a result of the diagrams presented and the agreements reached during the different meetings, we made an initial prototype, which could be tested by the experts of Co-design group and also by the internal experts and which allowed us once reviewed to go to the next phase, the implementation, which we describe in the point [3. Development](#)

The prototype implemented during this phase is available at the following public link <https://cos4cloud-2d9d3.web.app/>

2.3.5 Test

We defined a group of different tests, that we have carried out to check the correct working of implemented prototype:

1. Login ✓
2. Search
 - a. Search by species name. ✓
 - b. GBIF Backbone Species List Service Operation. ✓
 - c. Filtering:
 - i. By range: Plantae, Animalia, Fungi, Reptilia ✓
 - ii. By portal: Natusfera, iSpot. ✓
 - iii. By degree of research. ✓
 - iv. By chance degree. ✓
 - v. With photos. ✓
 - vi. With geolocalization. ✓
 - d. By area, operation of the [Nominatim](#). ✓
 - e. Combined search. ✓
 - i. Name and filter. ✓
 - ii. Name and area. ✓
 - iii. Filter and area. ✓
 - f. Download observations with CSV format
3. Access the detail of the observation. ✓
4. Add a comment. ✓
5. Add an Identification ✓
6. Logout. ✓
7. Local installation with docker. ✓

3. Engineering software design

3.1 Introduction

In this analysis phase we will pay attention to identifying the objectives that we have to develop in the General Purpose Expert Portal, doing a deep analysis to be able to implement the prototype in the best possible way.

3.2 Vision

The Expert Portal is a common framework for accessing Biodiversity or Environmental information, which will allow experts to perform quick and easy searches on multiple Citizen Science Observatories. This platform will help them to download information for their studies in a standardized way, without having to go to each Observatory, but also the experts will be able to contribute with their knowledge adding their identifications to the observations made by citizens, thus reducing the time investing during the identification process. The following questions can help to understand the added value of the Experts portal:

What are the differentiating elements and advantages?

As we have commented in the Executive summary section, the world of Citizen Science is relatively new in terms of technological development, so it is easy to make improvements and include new functionalities that provide added value.

The main element of the General Purpose Platform that makes the difference is that it will allow to combine both Biodiversity and Environmental information, which is not present in any platform right now and which is of vital importance to know many aspects related to distributions, behaviors or populations of the Flora and Fauna that surround us.

In addition, the Expert Portal establishes a starting point in the consensus between the different COs that will help to start working together and not as nodes without connection, this will help to:

- Increase the number of identifications.
- Reduce the time in which observations are validated.
- Increase the quality of identifications.
- Increase the number of experts participating.
- Be able to manage standardized information.

- Be able to know KPIs or measure the impact at a global level about the contributions made by the experts in the different COs.
- Be able to download all the Citizen Science information from a single site.

Are there products or services that offer something similar?

In the context of Biodiversity, the unique reference platform that aggregates information from different institutions or platforms is GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility). However, this global infrastructure has several different characteristics compared to the Expert Portal:

- GBIF is not a central Citizen Science system, it also contains Biodiversity information from scientific Institutions.
- GBIF is not a real-time aggregation system, it requires a complex publishing process.
- GBIF just contains validated information, that means, the scientific names of each observation have already been identified.

The last characteristic is what makes the Expert Portal a different platform than GBIF, since in GBIF there is no type of interaction between the community. It simply acts as a huge repository, where people can consult or publish the Biodiversity that exists at the Global level in a standardized way, but the most important is that it also does not contain Environmental information.

Is there an equivalent product or service?

As we mentioned in the previous section, GBIF is the service that most resembles it, in the Biodiversity information aggregation system characteristic, but the Expert Portal contains Citizen Science information in real time, it does not have complex publication processes and allows direct interaction between citizens and experts. The Expert Portal will offer a new service within the world of Citizen Science.

Is there a workaround that people are using that is good enough but not perfect?

Up until day we do not know a service that performs the work we are carrying out, so we can say that the Expert Portal is an innovative system at a Global level.

What does the competition do good and bad?

If we define GBIF as a possible competition of the Expert Portal, knowing the differences already mentioned in the previous sections, we can say as positive aspects that:

- GBIF has a very complex infrastructure that allows it to manage more than one thousand million records of information.

- Its organization is based on a system of national nodes in which each country pays an annual fee, which allows it to have the right to vote in the annual meetings, which gives stability to the organization.
- They have an open Community that makes contributions at different levels: technical, support, communication ...
- They are based on standards, and promote their use among the nodes that are part of the global network, which means that the same procedures are always followed, following the rules defined and validated by the Community.
- They actively participate in symposia and conferences that year after year give them more visibility and commitment.
- They have extensive experience, being a service that has been in operation for many years.

All these positive aspects will allow us in the future to define together with the Connect Group a sustainability and leadership strategy for the Expert Portal.

However, GBIF has a number of shortcomings due to its purely scientific nature, such as:

- There is no type of interaction with people, it works only as a repository of scientific information.
- It is not a real-time information system, it requires complex publication procedures.
- It only handles information on Biodiversity, when Biodiversity is much more than Flora and Fauna, since environmental variables have a direct impact.

3.3 Use Case Diagram

Use cases are functional requirements that indicate what the system will do. They are the main mechanism for the discovery of these requirements and their definition, in a way that they define the way in which the system will behave.

Figure 3.1. Use Case Diagram

3.4 Use cases

We can define a use case as the collection of success or failure scenarios, which describes the actors using the system to satisfy an objective.

To describe each of the use cases identified in the Use Case Diagram, we are going to use the full format, which shows us more details, is structured and allows us to better understand the objectives, tasks, and requirements of our system and how external actors interact with the software system that we want to develop.

3.4.1 UC1: Login

Lead Actor: Expert

Personnel and interests involved:

- Expert: you want to perform a safe and fast login.
- Authentication service: You want to receive authentication requests with the correct format and protocol.

Preconditions: The expert is identified and authenticated

Guarantees of success (Post-conditions): The expert authenticates to the system.

Main Success Scenario (or Basic Flow):

1. The Expert arrives at the portal with the intention of authenticating
2. Click on login and select Authenticate with Authenix.
3. The Authentication Service displays a series of options to authenticate.
4. The Expert selects Gmail as the authentication method.
5. The gateway requests username and password.
6. The Expert enters his username and password.
7. The Authentication Service authenticates the user in the Portal.
8. The Expert accesses the home page of the Portal already identified.

Extensions (or Alternative Flows):

*a. At any moment the System fails:

The system informs the Expert that an error has occurred, and asks him again to select an authentication method.

4a. The Expert selects Facebook as the authentication method.

4b. The Expert selects the Provider List as the authentication method.

1. The Expert searches by typing the name of the CO portal.
2. The Authentication System shows the filtered list.
 - 2a. The provider cannot be found.
 1. The Expert selects another authentication method.
3. The Expert selects the provider with which he wants to log in.

7a. Incorrect username or password.

1. Returns to step 5.

3.4.2 UC2: Search Observation

Lead Actor: Expert

Involved staff and interests:

- Expert: Expert wants to carry out a search in a quick and easy way, in order to make his contributions.
- Citizen Observatories (COs): COs want their data to be accessible to the community in a unified and global way.

Preconditions:

Guarantees of success (Post-conditions): The System displays search results.

Main Success Scenario (or Basic Flow):

1. The Expert enters the System in order to perform a search.
2. The System initially shows the latest observations made at citizen observatories.
3. The Expert repeats steps 3-4 until deemed necessary.
4. The Expert enters the name of a species in the search engine, selects a set of filters and a specific area.
5. The System shows all the results matching the species introduced by the Expert.
6. The Expert selects one of the results.
7. The System displays the detailed record of the observation.
8. The Expert consults the information on the observation file and exits the System.

Extensions (or Alternative Flows):

*a. At any time one of the Citizen Observatories does not respond to the search request.

1. The System reports the error to the Expert, sending him the corresponding incident so that he may take it into account, and continues with the visualization of the results.

4a. The System informs the Expert that it has not found any results in the search and to carry out a new search with other parameters.

- 5a. The Expert decides to download the list of results obtained **«extend»**

Download Observations.

1. The System informs the Expert that he must Login.
2. **«include» UC1 Login**
3. The System returns the search results in CSV format.

- 7a. The Expert decides to Add an ID **«extend» Add Identification.**
1. The Expert writes the identification in the Observation Record and clicks Add.
 - 1a. The Expert is not logged in.
 1. The System asks the Expert to login.
 2. The Expert login.
 2. The System sends the Identification to the Citizen Observatory origin of the Observation.
 - 2a. The Citizen Observatory does not respond and cannot register the identification.
 1. The System informs the Expert of the error and instructs him to try again later.
- 7b. The Expert decides to Add a Comment **«extend» Add Comment.**
3. The Expert writes the comment in the Observation Record and clicks Add.
 - 1a. The Expert is not logged in.
 1. The System asks the Expert to log in.
 2. The Expert logs in.
 4. The System sends the comment to the Citizen Observatory origin of the Observation.
 - 2a. The Citizen Observatory does not respond and cannot register the comment.
 1. The System informs the Expert of the error and instructs him to try again later.

3.5 System Sequence Diagram

To continue with the analysis and design process, we must know the behavior of our System, that is, what it does, without explaining how it does it, for which we will use the System Sequence Diagrams.

During the interaction described in the previous step between the actors and the System, a series of events is generated, requesting operations as responses. In this way with the SSD we will get a sample drawing, for each specific scenario of a use case.

We will see the SSD for UC1 and UC2 respectively, where the events can contain parameters and where the time advances downwards and the order of the events follows the same order as the one we have proposed in the use case.

3.5.1 Common Search

The SSD this essential scenario includes the system events of *searchObservations(name, filters, area)*, *getObservation(id, platform)*, *request_observations*

Figure 3.2. SSD Common Search

3.5.2 Add Identification

The SSD of Add Identifications includes the system events of *getObservation(id, platform)*, *addIdentification(id, platform, text)*, *putIdentification(id, text, user)*

Figure 3.3. SSD Add Identification

3.5.3 Add Comment

The SSD of Add Comment includes the system events of *getObservation(id, platform)*, *addComment(id, platform, text)*, *putComment(id, text, user)*

Figure 3.4. SSD Add Comment

3.5.4 Download dataset

The SSD of Add Comment includes the system events of *getObservations(id, source_platform)*, *generateDatasetCSV()*

Figure 3.5. SSD Download dataset

3.6 Domain model

The domain model allows us to show meaningful conceptual classes in our domain. This model is the visual representation of the conceptual classes where we do not define, following the UML notation, no operations, but:

- Objectives of the domain.
- Associations between conceptual classes.
- Attributes of conceptual classes.

Most of the classes identified in the model have been extracted from the description of the use cases and from the knowledge provided through the meetings by the different experts in each context.

Figure 3.6. Domain Model in the General Purpose Expert Portal Domain

4. Development

4.1 Introduction

In the development section we will explain the technology that we have used based on the Agile Methodology and Co-design. We will also do an explanation and an analysis from the point of view of the Frontend and Backend, to finally show an image of the system architecture.

4.2 Methodology

Additionally to Agile and Co-design methodology we focus on reaching milestones easy to achieve, to close the stages towards each objective defined in short sprints. To reach it we follow three basic principles: Simplicity, Communication and Feedback.

- **Simplicity:** the fewer elements disperse the attention of the objective, the easier it is to achieve.
- **Communication:** Indispensable. Each difficulty, doubt, comment or change is put in common to assess whether the final goal is achievable or what elements are prioritized over others.
- **Feedback:** The team seeks constant feedback from those responsible for the project, both when solving doubts, as well as to comment on positive points, strengths of the project, elements for improvement or possible changes. Thus, the team advances with confidence and with a clear objective.

4.3 Technology

In the technology section we explain at the Frontend and Backend level the decision making regarding the methodologies used in the development and the choice of each one of them.

4.3.1 Frontend

The frontend is designed with a component-based methodology. All modern component-based front-end frameworks make project management easy, which in turn helps make it a long-term, easy-to-maintain project.

The main factor of a component-based methodology is to reject pieces of code that are intended for multiple uses, and a clearer application architecture, and generally have a unified development process.

We have created 4 levels within the methodology:

- **Atom or Component:** they are the smallest blocks of the project, individual legos. We refer to text styles, buttons, icons, input fields, check boxes, etc. It does not depend on any other component or external agent to function.
- **Molecules or set of Components:** When we create a more complex component, and we need to reuse other components, this pattern of "molecules" arises. Like atoms, they do not depend on an external factor to function. For example, a search bar, a grid of images, etc.
- **Services:** They are pieces of code that aim to organize and share business logic, data and functions with different components and parts of an application. They provide very useful functions that help to divide the prototype into different small logical units that can be reused and that can be called from anywhere in the application, but strictly, it is each page that makes use of these services. For example, get data from a portal, add a comment, get credentials from an external service, etc.
- **Pages:** Pages are the modules that encompass and organize the previous levels. They are made up of multiple components and services. The main function is to organize and present the flow of data between services and components for its correct presentation.

These levels are reflected in the organization of the interface source code:

```
/components
  /pages
    ObservationsPage
    ObservationPage
    ProfilePage

/modals
  MapComponent

/shared
```

CommentComponent
DownloadComponent
GridComponent
SearchComponent

/services
MappingService (API endpoint)
GbifService
PlaceServices (Nominatim)

This organization offers us better communication and implementation with the team. Having a naming convention and interface organization play an important role in the success of a project. This results in less misunderstandings and much better implementation of designs and developments.

It is important to choose mature technologies because they are reliable. We have to understand that all technologies have a life cycle, so we need future-proof technologies.

The questions we must ask ourselves are:

What companies sponsor the development of the technology in question?

When large corporations are behind a technology, this means that in the short term it is difficult for the company to decide to abandon their support (although it can happen in some cases)

How big is the community?

The larger the community, the greater the chance that things will stick around for quite some time, and also give us continuous support and development updates of the tools and platforms.

What is long-term support like?

In this case, we care about long-term support.

Below we summarize a list of frameworks with their main characteristics:

React

React is maintained by Facebook. Large companies have incorporated this framework into their stack: Netflix, Dropbox, Pinterest, etc.

Advantage:

- React enjoys a large community.
- It stands out for its performance.
- It is easy to use.

Disadvantages:

- It has too many updates.
- Two ways to develop (Classes and Functional "hooks").

Vue

It is maintained by the community. Like React, large companies use it: Alibaba, Nasa, Gitlab, Nintendo, Amazon, etc.

Advantage:

- Flexible and simple to use.
- Stands out for its performance.
- Has great long-term support.

Disadvantages:

- The community is much smaller.
- It is not maintained by a large corporation.
- Two ways to develop (the classic and the "hooks").

Angular

It is maintained by Google. Some examples of companies that use them: Microsoft, Udemy, Paypal, etc.

Advantage:

- By default it uses TypeScript.
- It has a very stable and complex architecture (beneficial for large teams).

Disadvantages:

- The weight of the applications is enormous.
- The performance is worse than the previous ones.
- Version support is 6 months up to a maximum of 18 months.

Stencil

Stencil is a front-end framework maintained by Ionic (a leading company in the development of mobile applications with Javascript). What stands out about this company is its total focus on the sector. Some companies that use it: Apple, Amazon, Porsche, etc.

Advantage:

- It is the union of the best of the 3 previous frameworks.
- It uses TypeScript by default.
- Great performance.
- Very light.
- Future proof, as it generates standard web components.

Disadvantages:

- It is too new.
- The versioning policy is unknown (although we know it is a long term one).

For the expert portal, it has been decided to use Stencil, since it brings together the best of the most popular frameworks and does not lack any technology:

- Web Component-based.
- Asynchronous rendering pipeline.
- TypeScript support.
- One-way Data Binding.
- Component prerendering.
- Simple component lazy-loading.
- JSX support.
- Dependency-free components.

4.3.2 Backend

We need a backend to be able to map the observations of the different portals, perform the csv download and verify the credentials of the users using Authenix service. We could define the backend as the data access layer.

For this case we have used a very popular stack (Node - Swagger - Express - Docker):

- **Node:** We choose this framework because it is lightweight and is the same language as the frontend.
- **Swagger:** We need an API that maps the different portals (Natusfera, iSpot, PlantNet, ArtPortalen ...), for this we have documented the API with the Swagger specification.
- **Express:** Very popular node microframework, high performance and stable since 2012.
- **Docker:** Users can download the docker virtual container/image to install locally and make changes or customize the software when needed.

4.3.3 Architecture

The result of this structure of the Expert Portal is represented graphically as we can see below:

Figure 4.1. Architecture Expert Portal

Figure 4.2. Data Flow between Expert Portal and Citizen Observatories

4.4. Code

At this moment we all the code is available on a public GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/Bineo-Consulting/Cos4Cloud>

5. Future work

For the next phase, our goal is to get more feedback from the Co-design community to help us enrich the system. For this reason, during the second period, different meetings have been scheduled with those responsible for this Science for Change task, which will allow us to obtain more information about:

- How would the experts use this service?
- What do you find most interesting?
- What would they change?
- What do you think is not present?
- How do you think this service can contribute to the quantity and quality of information in the Citizen Observatories?
- And what problems do they identify?

We will also continue to participate in the Connect Group meetings. This group provides us a very important vision on how we could get more engagement of the different actors who may be interested in using this type of services, reach them through the official communication channels of Cos4Cloud and help them provide helpful documentation on the use of them.

From an implementation point of view, we will continue to work cyclically to progress on:

- The incorporation of the rest of COs.
- Reach a consensus with the COs on the minimum and common fields that should be shared through the Expert Portal.
- Include more filtering options.
- Include the capability to search for common names in multiple languages.
- Include the internationalization of the software not only at the front level but also the possibility of translating the comments included by other people in different languages.

- Define an interoperability layer that is easy to integrate for COs, which will help more COs to join the Expert Portal, for which we are thinking of creating an interoperability model based on 2 standards widely known and validated by the International Community, which are [Darwin Core](#) and [Darwin Core Archive](#).

The idea is to create a Mapping model based on these standards, which allows an easy integration into the Expert Portal System to current and future Observatories, hand in hand with an easy understanding of it, since this model is based on terms and concepts that are well known and frequently used in the contexts in which we operate.

Below we can see the diagram of the proposed Model.

Figure 5.1. Proposal Scheme interoperability model

6. Conclusions

As we analyzed at the beginning of the document, the world of Citizen Science is in continuous expansion and continuous change. There are more and more portals, each with a different information structure, there is no communication between some portals and others that allow the creation of a common network, so they work as disconnected nodes, and makes the integration process of COs in a complicated task:

1. The COs are not prepared to carry out a complex integration and they do not want to modify their technological structure much, if they do it it must be with the least effort.
2. They tend to be suspicious of sharing the information that users provide them both at the level of images and at the level of meta-information, as it is a value for them.
3. In some cases they provide very complex information that is closer to the world of Science than to the Citizen world, which implies that the percentages of observations are not very high in some cases.

Despite these difficulties, it is a great opportunity for the different observatories since we are creating a service that does not exist today. The most similar service is the GBIF infrastructure, but GBIF stores all the Biodiversity information globally, while the General Purpose Platform tries to combine the Biodiversity information provided by Citizen Science with the value of Environmental Variables, since the Biodiversity is not only Flora and Fauna but also environmental aspects that interact directly with nature, which makes it an innovative service.

On the other hand, although the service was designed as a tool for the aggregation of Biodiversity information, we have realized that we are also creating a community of Observers and Experts who will be able to interact with each other regardless of the platform from which they come. With both roles in mind, we not only want to focus on giving visibility to the work carried out by Citizens, but we also think that it will be important to give visibility to the work carried out by Experts through the portal, which will allow us to show relevant KPIs on the productivity generated. by the Portal of Experts in the context of Citizen Science.

Finally another very important thing that we want to remark is that we had to make an over-effort during this first period because we had to create, not only this comment framework, also we had to implement the particular customization for the biodiversity context. We think that this was a mistake on the Grant Agreement because, it not make sense implement a Cos4Bio ready to be tested during the definition process of General

Purpose Platform and this was a very big challenge for us, in which we had to spend more time than estimated at the beginning of this first period.

Glossary

Term	Description
Expert Platform	Prototype that integrates data from various citizen observatories, allowing the experts who access it to perform various operations such as: searches, downloads, identifications, comments, with the benefit of reducing the investment of time when finding data on which to investigate, and that allows increasing the degree of participation of experts in the processes of identification of the observations made by citizens.
Citizen Observatory (CO)	Web Portal that allows the interaction between Citizens and Scientists in obtaining data, be it data on flora, fauna, odors, temperatures, precipitation measurements, emissions ..., and that involves an identification process , validation, quality and study.
Observation	It is the element observed by a person or device, be it Flora, Fauna or an Environmental Variable.
Identification	When the observations are not known by the citizens, they are presented in a random state, not identified, since they lack the scientific knowledge to be able to define the observation with precision. For example: In the case of a magpie, it would be identified when a user identified it as Pica Pica, and defined it through its correct scientific name.
Casual status	An observation is accidental when it has received an identification, but this has not yet been validated by any expert in its corresponding Citizen Observatory.
Research grade status	An observation is scientific grade, when it has been identified and in turn has been validated by an expert.
Citizen	Person who participates in Citizen Observatories sharing their observations related to biodiversity or environment context that can be used by the scientific community.
Expert	Person with sufficient knowledge to be able to carry out identifications or scientists dedicated to the world of Biodiversity or the Environment.

Standard	It is a common framework validated by the community, in this case it applies to the use of communication protocols, the representation of information, the visualization of images and procedures.
Interoperability	We can define it, within the project, as the layer that allows the data from the different Citizen Observatories to coexist in the same environment. This layer allows the Expert Portal to understand the information in each portal, performing a mapping task and showing it to the end user in a unified and standardized way.
FAIR	FAIR are data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. A March 2016 publication by a consortium of scientists and organizations specified the "FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship" in Scientific Data, using FAIR as an acronym and making the concept easier to discuss.
Actor	it is something with behavior, such as a person, identified by a role, computer system or organization.
Scenario	Specific sequence of actions and interactions between the actors and the system under study.
SSD	In software engineering, a system sequence diagram (SSD) is a sequence diagram that shows, for a particular scenario of a use case, the events that external actors generate, their order, and possible inter-system events. (wikipedia)